

Table 2. Stability parameters for grain dimensions and chemical properties of some varieties.

Variety	Grain length			(mm)Length-width ratio			Chalkiness (%)			Amylose content (%)		
	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di
OM987-1	8.7	2.55	0.040	3.16	1.23	0.010	5	0.50	0.30	23.9	1.33	2.07
IR58082	7.8	0.15	0.050	3.01	0.83	0.007	5	1.35	0.20	24.3	0.54	4.41
MTL 105	7.7	0.51	0.001	2.66	1.76	0.010	1	1.06	0.08	26.3	0.90	2.75
OM269	8.5	1.17	0.040	3.41	0.70	0.005	1	0.62	0.05	26.4	1.43	2.45
IR53964-39	8.0	1.22	-0.0006	2.72	0.79	0.002	5	1.17	0.01	28.3	0.71	3.58
IR29723	8.0	0.46	-0.0006	2.88	0.68	0.016	5	1.39	0.40	28	1.18	3.45

Physical dimensions as well as chalkiness were very stable (Table 2), and responses of these varieties followed the linear model. For amylose content, however, responses were quite complex and considered unstable under different fertilizer levels.

The results indicated that milling quality and amylose content were unstable under different fertilizer dosages while grain dimensions and chalkiness were stable. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Inheritance of resistance to rice tungro spherical virus in some rice cultivars

L. A. Ebron and R. R. Yumol, IRRI; R. Ikeda, IRRI and Laboratory of Rice Breeding Methodology, National Agriculture Center (NARC), Kanondal, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305, Japan; and T. Imbe, IRRI

Many rice cultivars serve as sources of resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). RTSV resistance could be an important factor in controlling tungro disease because the vector, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, can transmit the rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) only when it has previ-

Reactions to RTSV of F₁ and F₃ progenies from crosses of 3 resistant rice cultivars with TN1 and crosses between resistant parents.

Cultivar/cross	Reaction ^a	F ₃ lines				χ^2	P
		Resistant	Segregating	Susceptible	Fit		
Utri Merah	R	-	-	-	-	-	-
Utri Rajapan	R	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pankhari 203	R	-	-	-	-	-	-
Taichung Native 1	S	-	-	-	-	-	-
Utri Merah/TN1 (F ₁)	S	62	66	13	7:8:1	2.279	0.25-0.50
TN1/Utri Rajapan (F ₁)	S	21	-	65 ^b	1:3	0.010	0.90-0.95
Pankhari 203/TN1 (F ₁)	M	41	71	40	1:2:1	0.671	0.70-0.8
Utri Rajapan/Utri Merah (F ₁)	R	118	0	0	-	-	-
Utri Rajapan/Pankhari 203 (F ₁)	R	167	0	0	-	-	-

^aR = resistant, M = moderately resistant, S = susceptible. ^bPooled segregating and susceptible reactions.

ously acquired RTSV. However, the genetics of resistance to RTSV infection in these cultivars is not fully understood.

We undertook this study to efficiently breed cultivars resistant to RTSV.

We studied RTSV-resistant cultivars Utri Merah (IRGC Acc. 16680), Utri Rajapan (Acc. 16684), and Pankhari 203 (Acc. 5999). The F₁ and F₃ progenies of crosses between resistant cultivars and Taichung Native 1 (TN1), a RTSV-susceptible cultivar, were tested to determine the mode of inheritance for resistance to RTSV infection. We also determined the allelic relationships of the resistance genes among the resistant cultivars.

Thirty seedlings in each F₃ line were tested for RTSV, except for the F₃ lines of Utri Merah/TN1, for which 60 seedlings were inoculated per line.

In the artificial inoculation, five 10-d-old seedlings were grown in a clay pot

Histogram of the infection rates with RTSV in the Utri Merah/TN1 F₃ lines.

and confined in a mylar cage for 4 h with 10 viruliferous GLH adults per seedling. The GLH adults were given 3 d of access on TN1 plants doubly infected with RTBV and RTSV to acquire both viruses prior to inoculation. We took 5-cm-long strips of the 2d and 3d youngest leaves of each seedling 2-3 wk after inoculation to detect RTSV by ELISA.

In Utri Merah/TN1, the F₃ progenies segregated into 62 resistant plants (RTSV infection was 0-20%), 66 segregating (21-75%), and 13 susceptible (76-100%) (see table), resulting in a good fit to a 7:8:1 ratio (see figure). The F₁ plants of Utri Merah/TN1 were susceptible to RTSV infection, clearly indicating that

Utri Merah has two recessive genes for resistance to RTSV.

The F₃ analysis in TN1/Utri Rajapan gave a segregation ratio of 1:3 and that in Pankhari 203/TN1 a 1:2:1 ratio, indicating monogenic control of resistance in both Utri Rajapan and Pankhari 203. The F₁ plants of the TN1/Utri Rajapan were susceptible to RTSV while those of Pankhari 203/TN1 showed an intermediate infection rate.

The allelism test between Utri Merah and Utri Rajapan revealed no segregation of F₃ progenies for susceptibility. The F₁ plants were resistant to RTSV infection. This suggests that the recessive gene in Utri Rajapan is the same as one of the two recessive genes in Utri Merah.

The F₃ lines of Utri Rajapan/Pankhari 203 also showed no segregation for susceptibility to RTSV infection and the F₁ plants were likewise resistant, suggesting the presence of the same gene that controls RTSV resistance in Pankhari 203. The inconsistency of dominance of both cultivars could be explained by a dominant GLH resistance gene in Pankhari 203, *Glh-1*, which might suppress RTSV infection.

From these findings, we propose two gene symbols: *tsv-1*, for a gene for RTSV resistance that is common in the three cultivars, and *tsv-2*, for the other gene in Utri Merah that may be used in breeding programs to diversify gene sources for RTSV resistance. ■

Pest resistance— insects

Gall midge biotype 5 identified in Moncompu, Kerala, India

K. P. V. Nair and D. Ambika Devi, Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Kerala, India

Four biotypes (1-4) of the Asian rice gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*) (Wood-Mason) from different rice-growing areas of India have been identified and evaluated. Many gall midge-resistant rice donors and cultures were susceptible at Moncompu, a gall midge-endemic area.

We evaluated 10 differentials in three major groups and susceptible check Taichung Native 1 (TN1), all with known reactions to the biotypes, during 1991-92 wet seasons. The entries were transplanted in early June and late June to allow for peak gall midge infestation. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 3-m rows for each variety at 15- × 15-cm spacing. Percentage of plant and tiller damage was recorded at 50 d after transplanting (DAT).

Potential donors Eswarakora (group 1) and Siam 29 (group 2) showed little damage while Velluthacheera (group 3) exhibited more damage. Up to 85% plant damage was recorded in TN1 (see table).

Reaction of promising cultivars to gall midge biotype 5. Moncompu, Kerala, India. 1991-92 wet seasons.

Group	Entry	Differential	Mean infestation for two seasons		
			Damaged plants (%)	Silvershoots (%)	
I	1	W1263	5.0	4.0	
	2	ARC6605	27.5	5.2	
	II	3	Phalguna	2.5	3.6
		4	ARC5984	2.6	4.6
III	5	CR-MR1523	40.4	12.3	
	6	Velluthacheera	37.5	10.9	
	7	Aganni	40.0	22.9	
	8	Ptb10	37.5	12.8	
	9	T1477	43.1	22.1	
IV	10	TN1	85.0	29.5	

Gall midge populations at Moncompu, Kerala, tend to be distinctly different from the four biotypes characterized earlier. They have been designated as

biotype 5, with the characteristic R-R-S-S pattern for the four groups of differentials. ■

Inheritance of whitebacked planthopper resistance

Le Thi Sen, University of Cantho, Cantho, Omon, Vietnam

We studied the mode of inheritance for resistance to the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) in six resistant local cultivars of rice in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam.

Seedlings at the one-leaf stage were artificially infested with second- and third-instar WBPH nymphs. Reactions of the seedlings were recorded when the susceptible check, Taichung Native 1

(TN1), was completely killed. Seedlings were scored as resistant when they showed reactions similar to those of the resistant check, and as susceptible when they were completely killed or severely stunted with signs of wilting. The reactions of F₁ and F₃ lines were scored on a row basis, while F₂ populations were scored on an individual seedling basis. For the F₃ lines, rows were scored as homozygous resistant, segregating, or homozygous susceptible.

The F₁ seedlings in all crosses were resistant, indicating that resistance was dominant in all six cultivars. The F₂